

Dopant effects on the structure and optical properties of the NaREF₄ oxyfluoride glass-ceramics

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ABSTRACT

Rare-earth (RE) doped nanostructured oxyfluoride glass-ceramics (GCs), have been widely studied due to the low phonon energy environments of fluorides (300-400 cm⁻¹) and the mechanical advantages of oxide glasses. The principal applications of these materials are in photonics, such as infrared and tunable phosphors [1], three-dimensional colour optical recording/displays, white light generation for ambient lighting, light frequency up-conversion lasers, and solar cells [2-4].

In order to develop RE doped nGCs with high emission efficiency, the key factor is to select an appropriate fluoride host. From the suitable crystalline hosts, NaREF₄ in the form of NaGdF₄ or NaLuF₄ have been considered as one of the excellent luminescent host matrices for various RE ions. They are used for photonics applications, such as up- and down- converter materials for sensitive in-vivo bioimaging [5,6]. On the other hand, the processing route is a key issue for a suitable preparation of these materials. The typical glass processing method is the melting–quenching (MQ). This synthesis method requires high melting temperatures with a limitation in the fluorine content. However, bulk materials and fibers can be easily obtained. Instead of most of the studies were performed on bulk samples, the possibility to prepare GC fibers is also becoming a hot-spot for novel optical materials.

In this work, 0.5Er³⁺ and 0.5Er³⁺-yYb³⁺ (y = 2, 4 mol%) doped transparent aluminosilicate oxyfluoride GCs with NaGdF₄ or NaLuF₄ nanocrystals ranging from 10 to 50 nm were obtained by the melt-quenching process and suitable thermal treatment in the different forms such as bulk and fibers. These last ones have been prepared for the NaLuF₄ samples by the rod-in-tube method and controlled crystallization. The crystallization process for both composition was investigated using X-ray diffraction and high resolution transmission electron microscopy among others, Fig. 1.

Fig.1 (a) XRD diffractograms for the un-doped, Er³⁺ doped and Er³⁺-Yb³⁺ co-doped d 70Si7Gd GC heat treated at 550 °C-120 h. (b) STEM-HAADF images of 0.5Er³⁺-2Yb³⁺ co-doped GCs used for the EDX analysis and (c) its corresponding EDX line scan spectra of one nanocrystal.

Optical characterisation was also performed employing UV-Vis absorption spectra together with excitation and emission spectra. Excited state dynamics revealed the up-conversion (UC) mechanisms. Moreover, the UC emission color changes from yellow to green by increasing the excitation power density which allows to manipulate the color output of the Er^{3+} emission in the GCs. This tuneable emission color is easily detected with the naked eye and quantify by CIE chromaticity coordinates diagram, see Fig. 2. Finally, the relationship between processing-structure-optical properties of these materials is discussed as a function of the dopant concentration and the shape of the synthesized GCs.

Fig.2. CIE chromaticity coordinates of the GC fiber for two different laser excitation densities, 2.5 and 0.75 kW cm^{-2} , respectively.

Keywords: Glass-ceramic, Melting-quenching, NaREF_4 , bulk and fibers, Up-conversion, Down-conversion.

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